

EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERIZATION OF STRAIN-RATE SENSITIVITY ON FAILURE PROPERTIES OF CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Concerning crashworthiness of composite structures, reliable designs require the detailed response of the composite material at high strain-rates. The general framework of this study lies in the development of test means and facilities to characterize the dynamic behavior up to the final failure of aircraft primary structure materials. These experimental results should feed into the reflection on the development of a modelling strategy suitable for crashworthiness numerical analysis. This research focuses on the experimental investigation of a unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminate, under static and dynamic loadings. The objective of this paper is to present the general approach used to experimentally analyze the strain-rate sensitivity of the failure envelope in tension as well as in compression. It relies on the use of off-axis specimens and tests conducted by means of the use of a servohydraulic jack. The main advantage of off-axis specimens lies in the apparent simplicity of tests that permit to induce coupled transverse/shear stress states by using a single actuator and simple specimen geometries. However, their drawbacks lie in the introduction of an unwanted transverse load on the dynamic devices and consequently in a more complex analysis of the tests. In this study, a specific focus is provided on the development of an experimental methodology aiming at reducing unwanted transverse loads concerning both tensile and compressive tests on off-axis specimens. A uniaxial load is therefore provided by means of the use of oblique tabs regarding the off-axis tensile tests. Concerning off-axis compression tests, a specific set-up has been developed to allow the transverse displacements and prevent friction between the specimen and the testing machine.

1 SCIENTIFIC CONTEXT AND INTRODUCTION

Due to their interesting strength-to-weight ratio, composite materials are now widely used in several fields of transportation industry. The strain rates of interest in aeronautic applications typically range from creep loading at $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$ to dynamic condition at $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$. When dealing with a crash situation, the rates of interest are usually reduced from quasi-static at $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ to dynamic at $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The analysis of the strain-rate effect on the mechanical behavior is therefore of a great interest to the design of crashworthiness structures made with composite materials. In order to consistently predict the crash response of aircraft structures and their consequences in terms of passengers' survivability, there is a need to enhance the confidence in the rate-dependent constitutive laws under a wide range of strain rates. Although advanced and robust modelling approaches for quasi-static loadings are widely available in literature, they do not seem to be the most relevant to be directly extended to explicit resolution schemes and therefore to industrial crashworthiness applications. A new ONERA strategy lies in the introduction of the rate dependency in a modelling law built with a mastered richness [1], in order to limit the complexity of the identification procedure and to unify static and dynamic approaches (Fig. 1). Within this context and focused on the

mesoscopic failure criterion at the unidirectional ply scale, the objective of this experimental work is to assess the rate dependency of the different parameters used in this model of this criteria. This relies on the proposal of several tests suited to both static and dynamic loads and to both tension and compression stress states.

Figure 1: General OPFM framework suitable for static and dynamic numerical analysis [1]

The failure of composite materials has been widely investigated under quasi-static conditions [2-4]. On the past decade, a significant effort has also been provided to improve confidence regarding the analysis of the strain-rate effects on failure properties of composite materials [5-8]. To experimentally characterize a failure criterion at the ply scale level, complex stress states must be induced in the specimen during the tests. In most studies, the mechanical characterization of the multiaxial strength of unidirectional composite materials relies on the use of off-axis specimens [9-12] because of their apparent simplicity. Nevertheless, the fully experimental characterization of the entire failure envelop still remains a challenge considering the potential effect of the experimental boundary conditions and the unwanted transversal load which is due to the angle between the material axes and the loading direction. The goal of this study consists on developing a methodology aiming at characterizing the rate dependency of the failure envelop over a wide range of aimed strain rates $\dot{\epsilon}$ between $= 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $= 10^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, by means of the use of a servohydraulic jack. A specific focus is also performed to minimizing the induced and harmful transversal load, as the dynamic device is not designed to sustain this kind of transverse load.

2 MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL ENVIRONMENT

The material used in this study is the Hexply M21/35%/268/T700GC (Hexcel France) made of carbon fibre and M21 epoxy resin. The unidirectional plates have been manufactured with a typical cure cycle in an autoclave after a hand lay-up procedure.

The experimental investigation is performed on a SCHENCK servo-hydraulic jack. In this study, three different upper holder speeds will be studied: 5 mm/min, 500 mm/min, and 1 m/s. For each speed, at least three specimens are tested in order to check discrepancies. The applied load is measured with a Kistler 9071A piezo-electric cell. Pre-stressing is performed on the load cell in order to be able to measure the applied load between -200 and +200 kN. To accurately evaluate the speed of the test, the upper holder displacement is measured with a Keyence laser transducer (KEYENCE LK-HD500 and LK-H052). A digital image correlation (DIC) measurement technique has been used to assess the homogeneity of the strain field prior to the failure and to measure macroscopic longitudinal strains. To record the images a high-speed Photron SA-X camera is used. Finally, to synchronize all measurement systems and record data, a 1-MHz DEWETRON DEWE-2600 data acquisition system is used.

Figure 2: Testing fixture of the Schenck servo-hydraulic jack used for all tests

3 FAILURE IN TENSION

3.1 Off-axis tensile specimens

As previously mentioned, the main issues regarding off-axis tensile tests rely on an unwanted transverse load, a more complex exploitation of the tests and a failure likely to occur near the tabs. In order to prevent from these issues, the investigated solution relies on the use of oblique tabs for off-axis specimens. In order to minimize the transverse load and to homogenize the stress fields, this solution has already been studied and apply on 10° off-axis tension specimens [13,14]. The computation of the angle of oblique tabs inspired from [14] is based on the hypothesis that off-axis specimens are submitted to a uniaxial state of stress $\sigma_{xx} = \sigma_0$, for which the strain of strain is given as:

$$\varepsilon_{xx} = \bar{S}_{11} \cdot \sigma_0 \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_{yy} = \bar{S}_{12} \cdot \sigma_0 \quad (2)$$

$$\tau_{xy} = \bar{S}_{16} \cdot \sigma_0 \quad (3)$$

where S_{ij} are the compliance coefficient in the global coordinate system. Assuming elastic deformation of the specimen, the angle ϕ which corresponds to the angle of the iso-displacement line with the longitudinal axis is given by:

$$\cotan(\phi) = -\frac{\bar{S}_{16}}{\bar{S}_{11}} \quad (4)$$

The figure Fig.3 summarizes the dimensions of the off-axis tension specimens used for high strain rate tests.

Figure 3: Oblique tab off-axis tension specimen geometries cutted in $[0]_4$ unidirectional lay-ups plate

Table 1 summarizes the correspondence between the off-axis angle of the specimen and the oblique angle of the tab for which quasi-static shear modulus are determined from [15].

θ ($^\circ$)	15	30	45	60	75
ϕ ($^\circ$)	23.5	37	56	74	85

Table 1: Correspondence between the off-axis angle θ and the oblique tab angle ϕ

3.2 Strain-rate effect on failure properties in tension

The figure Fig. 4 illustrates the failure envelop in the shear/longitudinal domain (Fig. 5.a.) and in the shear/transversal domain (Fig. 5.b.) for the three loading speeds considered in this study. As it can be seen, the failure envelops exhibit a rate dependency with the increase loading rate. Despite this observation, the trends obtained with regard to orientations from 45° onwards may be arguable.

Figure 4: Illustration of the failure envelop in tension for three loading speeds

The figure Fig. 5 shows the evolution of the oblique tab angle ϕ with the axis angle θ for both quasi-static and high strain-rate T700/M21 composite properties. Shear properties for static and dynamic are determined from [15]. It has to be noticed that the viscoelastic behavior of this material leads to some differences on the computation of the angles ϕ . It would have been consistent to modify the tab angles for high strain rates in order to avoid some questionable results on $\theta = 45^\circ$ and $\theta = 75^\circ$ (Fig. 5.b.). However and for high loading rates, the real experimental strain-rate is quite difficult to assess prior to performing tests. This could be considered as a limitation to consistent computations of tab angles prior to dynamic testing.

Figure 5: Oblique tab angle in function of the off-axis angle for T700/M21 properties

4 FAILURE IN COMPRESSION

4.1 Longitudinal compression

Tensile failure strength of CFRP materials is known to be un-sensitive to the increased strain-rate [16]. Conversely, the kinking mechanism involving the contribution of the matrix to the failure phenomenon leads to a rate sensitivity of the compressive failure properties [17,10]. The experimental investigation of the strain-rate dependency of the longitudinal failure strength is based on the recent ONERA testing procedure described in [18]. The key concept relies on a laminate designed in such a way that, when subjected to a tensile loading, fails by compressive failure in its central 90°-ply, due to Poisson effect, without any prior damage. As the specimen has been designed for quasi-static loading, a specific design had to be performed to be suitable for the maximum load capacity of the servo-hydraulic device and in order to achieve the maximum reachable strain-rate in the useful length (Fig. 6). The analysis of the experimental investigation in dynamic is under progress.

Figure 6: Design of the specimen for the identification of the longitudinal compressive strength by mean of a dynamic tensile loading

4.1 Off-axis compression

While relatively long specimens are suitable and stable for use in tensile tests, shorter and thicker specimens are more reliable for compressive tests in order to avoid global sample buckling phenomena. Nevertheless, it leads to additional difficulties such as high transverse loads in off-axis tests, high load levels relatively with the use of servo-hydraulic jack and potential risks of failure of the specimen at the boundary conditions. Consequently, a new and dedicated set-up for compression tests of off-axis specimens suitable for dynamic loadings has been developed (Fig. 7).

a.

b.

Figure 7: a. Experimental set-up for off-axis compression test, b. Longitudinal strains on a 15° off-axis specimen under quasi-static compression loading

In order to reduce transverse loads and to guarantee a uniform state of stress during dynamic off-axis experiments, the solution proposed in this study relies on the use of an original end-loaded compression technique. The upper end-surface of specimen is loaded through a punctual-contact by means of an intermediate hemispherical component which is solidarized with the specimen. This prevents of any friction and edge effect and guarantees a uniaxial load until failure. The lower end-surface of specimen is seated on a radial ball-bearing and allows transverse displacements. With this device the transverse load is successfully avoided. This technical solution has been validated for quasi-static conditions and an experimental campaign from quasi-static to dynamic strain-rates using servo-hydraulic jack is under progress.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The present study aims at presenting a global approach for the experimental investigation of the strain-rate sensitivity of the failure properties of a CFRP material at the unidirectional ply scale both for tension and compression loadings. In order to characterize the influence of the increased strain rate on the parameters of a unified static/dynamic modelling law. Consequently, an experimental procedure based on reliable tests performed from static to dynamic loading has been developed. A specific focus has been provided to avoid harmful effects due to unwanted transverse loads and in order to be suitable to servohydraulic device for which the extensive experimental investigation is conducted over a wide range of strain rates.

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